

A social media mining approach to disaster relief management efforts: Hurricane Harvey

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ABSTRACT

Natural disasters such as hurricanes cause long lasting life changing events for the people in the affected areas. Over time, the social media platforms like Twitter have proved to aid the relief works done by social organizations and people in the event of the disaster. Social media is being used more and more to generate disaster awareness and the relief work required in the affected areas. Through our research we analyze tweets related to Hurricane Harvey by using a different set of n-grams and feeding the refined tweets to three different classifiers – Naive Byes, Logistic Regression and SVM. We classify these tweets in three categories: donation, relocation and volunteering. This is done for tweets generated during the event and at different times after Hurricane Harvey dissipated. We then compare the results of the classification for the different periods. We conclude our research with the observation that the tweets related to donation, relocation and volunteering are a small percentage of the total tweets published during the disaster and these numbers tend to decrease further over time. However, tweets related to donations are still somehow relevant months after Hurricane Harvey.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural disasters, such as hurricanes, earthquakes and forest fires, bring hardship to mankind living in the affected areas. The hardship and the damage caused by these natural disasters can last for several months, even years, after its occurrence. Every few years, the Atlantic hurricanes batter Southern United States bringing heavy rains and flooding to low lying towns/cities. Hurricane Harvey is one such example which recently hit the city of Houston, in the State of Texas, causing extensive damage to life and property. Social Media such as Twitter contain valuable disaster

related data which can throw light on the kind of damage, relief efforts, and the effectiveness of disaster response.

The goal of this research is to analyze the tweets from the social network Twitter related to Hurricane Harvey over different periods in time, during and after its occurrence and track the relief management efforts. To achieve this, we defined a set of n-grams for each of the categories and extracted random tweets based on these. The tweets were then annotated manually, pre-processed and fed to the classifiers for training the model.

2. RESEARCH

2.1 Main Idea

The scope of the study is based on training the classifiers into the broader categories of “Relocation”, “Donation” and “Volunteering” with tweets that were published during the disaster. Then, we used the fitted model to classify Hurricane Harvey tweets from other time periods and compare the occurrences of the categories across periods.

The following steps were followed during our research:

1. Extract and prepare data from archived Hurricane Harvey Twitter dataset based on specific set of n-grams for each category
2. Generate random tweets for each member of the team to perform manual annotation
3. Use Fleiss’ kappa [10] as a method to measure inter-rater reliability
4. Train the classifiers using the manually annotated tweets
5. Obtain tweets for other time periods using the GOT [9] module
6. Test the classifiers against multiple time periods (August, 2017 until April, 2018)

5. Compare the results of classifiers for data sets from multiple time periods

2.2 Related Work and novel contribution of our research

There is plenty of literature that uses Twitter to collect data that can be used for sentiment analysis of messages related to crisis and disasters. Verma et al [1] created an approach for automatically identifying messages communicated via Twitter that contributed to situational awareness in a moment of crisis. They collected tweets from multiple crisis events (Red River Floods, Oklahoma Grass Fires and Haiti Earthquake) and created a prediction model utilizing a combination of “hand-annotated” and “automatically extracted” features. The use of manual labeling for training data sets is something common in multiple papers ([2], [3], [4] and [5]). This helps in creating a better training data set that can aid in increasing the accuracy of the classification. Another study done by Chowdhury et al in 2013 [6] focuses not only on identifying disaster related tweets but also classifying them in periods such as pre-incident, during-incident and post-incident. Even though these studies provide a great deal of information related to identifying and classifying tweets for disaster related events, they look at periods of time that are very close to the incident. However, little is known about the mid/long term impact of the disasters. We would like to bridge this gap by analyzing tweets that are published months after the incident that provide further visibility of the aftermath and recovery process.

2.3 Data Acquisition and Wrangling

To train our model we obtained tweets from an archived Hurricane Harvey Twitter dataset that was downloaded from the University of Northern Texas Digital Library [7]. The dataset covers the period from 08/18/2017 until 09/22/2017 and contains 7,041,866 unique tweets in JSON format. The dataset was first loaded to a Mongo DB instance and then exported using the *mongoexport* [8] utility.

The training data extraction and preparation involved the following steps:

1. Obtain the publicly available archived Twitter data related to Hurricane Harvey [7]
2. Load the data into a document database. We used Mongo DB for loading and extracting the publicly available archived Twitter data.

3. Extract a random set of 1,000 tweets from the archived data for the most frequent bigrams for each category. For example, in the case of donation the following bigrams were used: “blood donation”, “donate blood”, “need blood”. Then, for the case of relocation: “temporary relocation”, “opening shelter”.
4. Generate a random set of 85 tweets from each of these categories and shuffle. Split the tweets evenly among team members and manually annotate them using the categories of “Relocation”, “Donation” and “Volunteering”.
5. We use Fleiss kappa [10] calculation to measure the agreement among annotators for a subset of the same tweets. We obtained a result of $k=0.32$, which means a fair agreement.
6. The tweets where we did not agree were further revised and we performed a second set of annotations with an updated criterion.
7. The manually annotated file was pre-processed and then used to train the classifiers.

2.4 Models and Methods

2.4.1 Defining Disaster relief classification

For the purposes of our research, we classify and analyze the major categories as donation, relocation and volunteering. We believe that these three classifications are significant in any disaster relief effort. For tweets with ambiguous text or text classifiable to more than one category, the n-gram weights will come into play. In this research, we did not consider tweets with no relief terms at all in our training data.

We used a different set of n-grams (unigrams and bigrams) to select tweets related to the three categories for the initial annotation step. These are examples of bigrams used for each of the categories:

Donation: “donate blood”, “blood donation”, “blood drive”, “need blood”, “give blood”, “red cross”, “blood supply”, “accepting donation”, “donation help”, “donate money”, “need money”, “give money”

Relocation: “temporary relocation”, “shelter place”, “take shelter”, “seek shelter”, “need transportation”, “people transportation”, “shelter opening”

Volunteering: “first responder”, “need volunteer”, “volunteer needed”, “volunteer help”, “need help”

2.4.2 Approach

Our approach is to use multiple machine learning classifiers and feature extractors. The machine learning classifiers are Multinomial Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression with and without SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) and Support Vector Machines with and without SGD. We applied a 5-fold cross validation and used the F1 weighted scores to evaluate the performance of the different classifiers.

2.4.3 Emoticons and Punctuations

We assumed emoticons and punctuations to be noisy labels for our disaster relief classification and hence strip them out from our training and test data. Had we left the emoticons & punctuations, then the accuracies for Logistic Regression and SVM would have been impacted because of the noisiness they bring in, with Naïve Bayes as an exception. The difference is due to the way in which some models make the feature weight selection. Stripping them out allows the classifiers from other less noisy features present in the tweet.

2.4.4 Feature Reduction

The distinct properties of the languages used in tweets are considered for reducing the feature space. Equivalence class tokens are used to filter for usernames, retweets, URL, images and repeated tweets to trim feature space. Additionally, alphanumeric words are removed from the tweets. Then, we apply a combination of WordNet lemmatization, Porter and Lancaster stemming on the set of unigrams and bigrams.

2.4.5 Machine Learning Models

We test different classifiers: Multinomial Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression with and without SGD and Support Vector Machines with and without SGD.

2.4.5.1 Multinomial Naïve Bayes

Multinomial Naïve Bayes is a simple model based on applying Bayes theorem with a naïve assumption that every feature is independent of the others, in order to predict the category of a given tweet. There are two options for feature engineering when applying Naïve Bayes classifiers: word frequency and tf-idf. We chose tf-idf because it not only counts the occurrence of a word in a given tweet, but also reflects how important the word is to the tweet across documents. The frequency-based probability might introduce zeros when multiplying the probabilities, leading to a failure

in preserving the information contributed by non-zero probabilities. Hence, we use Laplace smoothing coefficient ($\alpha = 1$) to counter this problem.

2.4.5.2 Logistic Regression

Our second algorithm for classification is called multinomial logistic regression. Logistic Regression is log-linear classifier that works by extracting a set of weighted features from the tweets, taking logs and combining them linearly without making independence assumptions for its features. Hence, we can add features like bigrams and phrases to Logistic Regression without worrying about features overlapping.

The weight vectors decide the significance of a feature. A higher weight means the feature is a strong indicator for the class. Finding the weights that maximize the strength is a convex optimization problem, so we use hill-climbing stochastic gradient descent method (SGD) and added smoothing (L1 regularization). We found that Logistic Regression performs better than Naïve Bayes because it handles feature overlap better. (Refer table below)

2.4.5.3 Support Vector Machines

We built our third classifier using Support Vector Machines algorithm. SVMs are great for text categorization as they work well in high dimensional spaces with few irrelevant features. With their ability to generalize well in high dimensional space and understand interactions between features when using non-linear kernels, SVMs eliminate the need for feature selection. This makes text categorization easier, speeding up overall processing. Similar to what we did in Logistic Regression, we use SGD with L1 regularization.

2.4.6 Model Evaluation

2.4.6.1 Experimental Set-up

For our research we have gathered tweets from two data sources:

a) Hurricane Harvey tweets domain collected and maintained by University of North Texas [1] between August and September, 2017. The tweets from this source are extracted for annotation and uses as our training set.

b) Twitter library GOT [9], which provides access to historical tweets by simulating searches through the Twitter web client. This is used to test our model.

Since the Twitter API has a limitation on the number of tweets that can be obtained as a response to any request, we use the GOT [9] module to extract historical tweets based on the date parameter. The module has a parameter that allows us to specify the search term and the number of tweets. The tweets in our testing set are from the time period between August 2017 to April 2018.

The tweets are then post-processed with the following filters:

1. Convert words in tweets to lowercase to consolidate same words with different capitalizations and help reduce feature space.

2. Replace links, usernames (@), hashtags (#), images, numeric values and retweets (RT) with blank values. These filters will serve to reduce noise and trim feature space. If these filters are not in place, then the Logistic Regression and SVM classifiers will assign weights on these which could affect accuracy.

2. Duplicated tweets are removed. The removal of RT generate repeated tweets and these can also be found in the data sources used. Similar to the filters applied, duplicates are removed to avoid putting extra weight on any particular tweet.

4. Apply lemmatization or stemming to reduce inflectional forms. This allows related words to be reduced to the same base or stem. For example, "donated" and "donation" can be reduced to "donat".

2.4.6.2 Testing set preparation

We collected the test data using GOT for a period of nine months from August, 2017 to April, 2018. The query terms used are listed below:

- a) '#HurricaneHarvey',
- b) '#Harvey2017',
- c) '#HarveyRelief'

After extracting the tweets, we create a data frame for each month and store these as Pickle files. We then loop over each of the Pickle files, look for duplicates and drop them if any. We also apply the filtering method to these tweets before passing these to the classifiers.

2.4.6.3 Model tuning

We use Grid Search to find the best parameters for a particular model. This method works by performing an exhausting search over specified parameters.

The parameters used with their corresponding values include the following:

- a) ngram_range': [(1,1),(1,2)]
- b) alpha': (1e-1, 1e-3, 1e-5)
- c) max_iter': (10,50,100)
- d) penalty': ('l1','l2','elasticnet')
- e) fit_intercept': (True,False),
- f) class_weight': (None,'balanced')
- g) warm_start': (True, False)

However, to predict the categories of tweets contained in the .pkl files, we decided to use Logistic Regression with SGD to ensure reproducibility of our experiments.

To increase reliability of the prediction we define a threshold value of 0.5. That is, a tweet is classified as belonging to a category only if the probability is higher than 0.5. If a tweet does not meet this threshold, then it is marked as not classified.

2.5 Visualizations

Figure 1 and 2. Evolution of breakdown of categories by time period (August, 2017 to April, 2018)

Figure 3. Most frequent words found in tweets classified as Donation.

Figure 4. Most frequent words found in tweets classified as Relocation.

Figure 5. Most frequent words found in tweets classified as Volunteering.

Figure 6. Words with the highest coefficients in Logistic Regression model

Figure 7. Words with the lowest coefficients in Logistic Regression model

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We explore the usage of unigrams, bigrams, unigrams and bigrams, and parts of speech as features. The table below shows the F1 scores of the different models.

Models	F1 Weighted score					
	(1,1) gram LC Stemmer	(1,1) gram PT Stemmer	(1,1) gram WN Lemmatizer	(1,2) gram LC Stemmer	(1,2) gram PT Stemmer	(1,2) gram WN Lemmatizer
Multinomial NB	89.0%	90.2%	89.0%	91.4%	92.2%	92.5%
Logistic Regression	91.8%	93.3%	93.4%	94.5%	94.5%	95.3%
Logistic Regression with SGD	93.0%	93.7%	94.5%	92.6%	95.3%	94.9%
SVM	87.8%	86.7%	87.5%	91.4%	92.4%	92.4%
SVM with SGD	95.7%	95.3%	95.7%	95.3%	96.1%	95.7%

Table 1. F1 Weighted Scores

Unigrams: The unigram feature extractor combined with stemming and lemmatization is the simplest and the robust way to retrieve features from a tweet. As we can see in Table 1., SVM with SGD achieves the best F1 score (96.1 %) among the different models using Lancaster Stemmer, Porter Stemmer and WordNet Lemmatizer methods.

Bigrams: We experimented with bigrams to see if tweets that contain key words and phrases like ‘donate blood’, ‘red cross’ and ‘relief effort’ would improve F1 scores. From the table above, we see that using a range of n-grams from 1 to 2 improved the F1 score across most models except when using the Lancaster Stemmer with Logistic Regression and SVM with SGD.

Although bigrams tend to be very sparse, the overall accuracy improves in the case of Multinomial Naïve Bayes and Logistic Regression for all methods, and SVM + SGD with Porter Stemmer.

In general using only bigrams as features is not useful because the feature space is very sparse. It is better to combine unigrams and bigrams as features.

Stemming and Lemmatization: Stemming and lemmatization algorithms removes the common morphological endings from words in English thereby using only the root words as features. We found significant improvements in accuracy when using these methods while processing the tweets.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we have proposed the analysis of tweets published both during and after a natural disaster such as Hurricane Harvey. For this purpose, we defined three categories relevant to relief efforts: donation, relocation and volunteering. We have built a training set focused on these categories and used a set of features to classify tweets in different periods after Harvey dissipated. We have seen that features such as unigrams and bigrams in combination with Lemmatizers and Stemmers achieved

the best performance, particularly using SVM classifier with SGD.

This research shows that less than 30% of the tweets related to Hurricane Harvey are dedicated to relief efforts and that this tends to decrease even further over time. However, we note that donation tweets are still appearing even multiple months after the incident.

Finally, there are a few things that could be done to extend this research. The training set considered a small set of tweets and these were labeled manually with a fair inter rating agreement. This could be further improved to consider a larger set of tweets with a better inter rating agreement score. Additionally, we found a large number of tweets that were not classified to any of the categories we have defined. That means, there are probably other categories that should be considered to identify the topics of most tweets during a natural disaster like Harvey.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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